

HISTORICAL VIEW OF USAGE OF DICTIONARIES

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Annotation: The article covers important background information about dictionaries: from history until now. Moreover, in the article types of modern dictionaries and ways of their usage were noted.

Key words: *quality of education, bilingual dictionary, monolingual, learner dictionary, subject-specific, etymologies, lexicographers.*

In today's process of globalization, the effect of the radical reform of the education system of Uzbekistan is evident in all areas related to this area. The state pays special attention to the teaching and further development of foreign languages in the education system, which is a key sector of socio-economic, political and cultural life of the country, one of the vital factors that directly affect the morale of the population. at the policy level. At a video conference chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev on May 6, 2021 on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, the problems in the system were analyzed in detail and priorities were identified. On this basis, the issue of attitudes to foreign language teaching is addressed in the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 No PP-5117 "On measures to bring the promotion of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level": "... education in foreign languages. It is no coincidence that the need to develop as a policy priority, radically improve the quality of education in this area, attract qualified teachers to the field and increase the population's interest in learning foreign languages "[1]. Of course, the role of dictionaries in perfect language learning is incomparable. Here, an interesting

question is "when and by whom was the first dictionary created?". This interesting question is sure to interest any person. We look at the history of creating dictionaries with our article.

A dictionary is one of the most important tools during your time studying at a university. A good dictionary can help you understand your subject better, improve your communication and improve your grades by making sure you are using words correctly. However, not all dictionaries are the same and if you don't know how to use a dictionary correctly, it could actually teach you the wrong meaning of a word and make it more difficult to get a good grade. A bilingual dictionary is a dictionary that has the word you are looking for translated into your own language. A bilingual dictionary usually only has a small amount of information about the word you are looking for but it is easy to understand because it is written in your native language. A monolingual dictionary is written only in English. A monolingual dictionary has lots of different information about every word in English. These dictionaries have lots of information about grammar and pronunciation. A monolingual dictionary can sometimes be confusing because it has multiple definitions for every word. A learner dictionary is similar to a monolingual dictionary because it is only in English and has lots of information about the word you are trying to find. However, a learner dictionary is a little bit easier to use than a standard monolingual dictionary and has clear examples and simplified language. A subject-specific dictionary is similar to a monolingual dictionary but it does not contain the general meaning of words, only the definitions that are suitable for the specific subject. Subject-specific dictionaries are very useful when you need to find out how a word is used differently in your subject area but they can be quite difficult to use and might not contain the word you are looking for[2].

Reference work that lists words, usually in alphabetical order, and gives their meanings and often other information such as pronunciations, etymologies, and variant spellings. The first recorded dictionaries date back to [Sumerian](#) times

around 2300 BCE, in the form of bilingual dictionaries, and the oldest surviving monolingual dictionaries are [Chinese dictionaries](#) c. 3rd century BCE. The first purely English alphabetical dictionary was [A Table Alphabeticall](#), written in 1604, and monolingual dictionaries in other languages also began appearing in Europe at around this time. The systematic study of dictionaries as objects of scientific interest arose as a 20th-century enterprise, called [lexicography](#), and largely initiated by [Ladislav Zgusta](#)[3]. The birth of the new discipline was not without controversy, with the practical dictionary-makers being sometimes accused by others of having an "astonishing" lack of method and critical-self reflection.[4] The first edition of [A Greek-English Lexicon](#) by [Henry George Liddell](#) and [Robert Scott](#) appeared in 1843; this work remained the basic dictionary of Greek until the end of the 20th century. And in 1858 was published the first volume of the [Deutsches Wörterbuch](#) by the [Brothers Grimm](#); the work was completed in 1961. Between 1861 and 1874 was published the Dizionario della lingua italiana by [Niccolò Tommaseo](#). Between 1862 and 1874 was published the six volumes of A magyar nyelv szótára (Dictionary of Hungarian Language) by Gergely Czuczor and János Fogarasi. [Émile Littré](#) published the [Dictionnaire de la langue française](#) between 1863 and 1872. In the same year 1863 appeared the first volume of the [Woordenboek der Nederlandsche Taal](#) which was completed in 1998. Also in 1863 [Vladimir Ivanovich Dahl](#) published the [Explanatory Dictionary of the Living Great Russian Language](#). The [Duden](#) dictionary dates back to 1880, and is currently the [prescriptive](#) source for the spelling of German. The decision to start work on the [Svenska Akademiens ordbok](#) was taken in 1787.

The earliest dictionaries, such as those created by Greeks of the 1st century CE, emphasized changes that had occurred in the meanings of words over time. The close juxtaposition of languages in Europe led to the appearance, from the early Middle Ages on, of many bilingual and multilingual dictionaries. The movement to produce an English dictionary was partly prompted by a desire for

wider literacy, so that common people could read Scripture, and partly by a frustration that no regularity in spelling existed in the language. The first purely English dictionary was Robert Cawdrey's A Table Alphabetical (1604), treating some 3,000 words. In 1746–47 [Samuel Johnson](#) undertook the most ambitious English dictionary to that time, a list of 43,500 words. [Noah Webster](#)'s dictionary of Americanisms in the early 19th century sprang from a recognition of the changes and variations within language. The immense Oxford English Dictionary was begun in the late 19th century. Today there are various levels of dictionaries, general-purpose dictionaries being most common. Modern lexicographers (dictionary makers) describe current and past language but rarely prescribe its use[5].

To sum up, it should be highlighted that there are several advantages in the use of dictionaries. In the very early stages of learning, even an inadequate bilingual dictionary can provide an important support and be a quick reference book. In language learning/teaching process the importance of using dictionaries cannot be denied. It is obvious that the dictionary can be an extremely useful learning resource, especially as it makes the learner more independent of the teacher. If the students learn how to use a dictionary effectively, then the dictionary can be a very helpful resource for their studies. Training in the proper use of a dictionary will be of help in selecting the meaning that is appropriate to a given context. The most important basic skill in using a dictionary is to find a word or expression one has in mind.

References:

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